

Figure S1. Cumulative amplified samples by latitude and depth, in the 2019 and 2021 sample years. Colored lines show the cumulative total number of samples with observed (amplified) eulachon eDNA. Dashed vertical line indicates the latitude of the mouth of the Mad River, the southernmost river with recorded eulachon spawning activity. Note that more sampling was performed in the southern portion of the domain in 2021 than in 2019.

Figure S2. Maps by year (rows) and depth category (columns) of the temperature covariate used in the final eulachon model.

Figure S3. Maps by year (rows) and depth category (columns) of the krill index covariate used in the final eulachon model. The selected krill metric was derived from the raw krill NASC values. Each grid cell in each depth category represents an inverse distance-weighted mean of its five nearest-neighbor NASC values. Values are depth-integrated, so are identical across depth categories.

Standards: Binary

Figure S4. Fit of selected model (Bernoulli portion of main text Equation 6) to the eulachon qPCR standards. For each PCR plate separately, this part of the model relates known concentrations of eulachon eDNA to the probability of amplification.

Standards: Positive

Figure S5. Eulachon qPCR standard curves for all successfully amplified samples (Equation 6, main text). For each PCR plate separately, this part of the model relates known concentrations of eulachon eDNA to the PCR cycle at which amplification is observed.

Unknown Samples: Pres/Abs

Figure S6. Fit of selected model (Bernoulli portion of main text Equation 5) to the unknown eulachon samples (i.e., the field samples), relating the predicted probability of amplification to whether or not amplification was actually observed. Blue curves are loess smooths, and the dashed red line is the 1:1 line where predicted equals observed.

Unknown Samples: Positive

Figure S7. Predicted vs. observed Ct for all unknown eulachon samples that successfully amplified, displayed by year (columns) and depth categories (rows). Blue curves are loess smooths, and the dashed red line is the 1:1 line where predicted equals observed.

Figure S8. Test of INLA mesh complexity. We varied the minimum interior edge length in the `sdmTMB::make_mesh` function, then used `sdmTMB` with cross-validation to fit the same model with each mesh. The red boxes indicate the selected mesh, with a minimum interior edge length of 40 km and 118 mesh vertices. The reason that the higher-likelihood meshes were not chosen was because models fit with these meshes proved too complex to accommodate more than 2 environmental predictors. Our chosen mesh therefore represents a tradeoff between mesh complexity and the ability to test and incorporate environmental predictors in the eulachon SDM.

Figure S9. Selected INLA mesh used in the final eulachon model, with locations of samples overlaid. The final mesh has 118 vertices, with a triangle edge length of 40km.

a

95% p(presence) TRUE

Figure S10. Predicted distribution of eulachon eDNA in California coastal waters, including (a) estimated concentration in log(copies/L) and (b) all areas with at least a 95% probability of presence of eulachon eDNA. Bathymetric lines indicate the 150m isobath.